

Efficient Solvers and Preconditioning Techniques for Generalized Sylvester Matrix Equations

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Abstract—In this paper, we present the block generalized minimal residual (BGMRES) method in order to solve the generalized Sylvester matrix equation. However, this method may not be converged in some problems. We construct a polynomial preconditioner based on BGMRES which shows why polynomial preconditioner is superior to some block solvers. Finally, numerical experiments report the effectiveness of this method.

I. INTRODUCTION

C

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$$AXB - X = C, \quad (1)$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times s}$, and X is the unknown matrix in $\mathbb{R}^{n \times s}$. The matrix equation (1) plays an important role in control and communication theory; see [3], [4]. Also, the discrete -time time -invariant linear systems

$$x_{k+1} = Ax_k + Bu_k,$$

$$y_k = cx_k,$$

$k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ and x_0 is given. These systems are associated, for instance, with the discrete -time Lyapunov equation

$$AXA^T - X = -BB^T.$$

It arises naturally in a wide variety of control applications such as stability analysis [17] model order reduction [12], [15], [18] and Newton's method for discrete algebraic Riccati equations [2]. The discrete-time Lyapunov equation is a special case of matrix equation (1).

The analytical solution of the matrix equation (1) has been considered by many authors; see [6]. They have proposed the Bartels-Stewart algorithm for solving matrix equation (1). The direct methods for solving the matrix equation (1) such as those proposed in [6], [7] are attractive if the matrices are of small size. These methods are based on the Schur's decomposition, by which the original equation is transformed into a form that is easily solved by a forward substitution. In recent years, several iterative methods based on the Arnoldi process have been proposed to solve

the matrix equation (1). For example, in [1], Bao et al. proposed an iterative method which allows us to construct an orthonormal basis of certain

Krylov subspace and simultaneously reduce the order of the generalized Sylvester equation (1). By the same token, in [3], Bouhamidi et al. proposed the global generalized minimum residual (GL - GMRES) to solve the following general linear matrix equations:

$$\sum_{j=1}^p A_j X B_j = C,$$

and then they applied ILU (incomplete LU factorization) and SSOR preconditioning in order to solve the Sylvester equation $AX + XB = C$. Here, we use ILU and SSOR preconditioning the same as the methods that [3] were used.

In this paper, we generalize the GMRES method to obtain a matrix iterative method to solve the matrix equation (1). Also, we present a polynomial preconditioner. Then, we compare these methods with BGMRES (ILU), BGMRES (SSOR) and NSCG [19], squared Smith (SM) and restarted Krylov squared Smith (RKSS) [10], [16] methods. Finally, we show that PBGMRES is more effective than the other methods.

Let $X = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_s]$, where $x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, s$ is i th column of X . We define a linear operator

$$\begin{aligned} \text{vec} : \mathbb{R}^{n \times s} &\longrightarrow \mathbb{R}^{ns} \\ X &\longmapsto [x_1^T, x_2^T, \dots, x_s^T]^T \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Hence, the linear matrix equation (1) can be written as the following $ns \times ns$ linear system

$$Ax = c, \quad (3)$$

where $A = (B^T \otimes A - I_{ns})$, $x = \text{vec}(X)$, $c = \text{vec}(C)$ and \otimes denotes the Kronecker product, see [4]. This product satisfies the properties

$$(A \otimes B)(C \otimes D) = (AC \otimes BD), (A \otimes B)^T = A^T \otimes B^T.$$

Equation (3) has a unique solution if and only if the matrix A is nonsingular.

Throughout this paper, we use the following notations: Let $X, Y \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$, the Frobenius inner product is defined $\langle X, Y \rangle_F = \text{tr}(X^T Y)$, where $\text{tr}(\cdot)$ denotes the trace and X^T the transpose of the matrix X . The associated norm is the well-known Frobenius norm denoted by $\|\cdot\|_F$. A system of matrices of $\mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$ is said to be F-orthogonal, if it is orthogonal with respect to the scalar product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_F$, that means $\text{tr}(X^T Y) = 0$. The Kronecker product of $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times q}$ is defined by $A \otimes B := [a_{ij} B] \in \mathbb{R}^{mp \times nq}$. We use the notation $*$ for the following product [8], [9], let V_m

where

$$AGK_m(A, R_0, B)B = \text{span}\{AR_0B, A^2R_0B^2, \dots, A^mR_0B^m\},$$

and

$$AK_m(A, r_0) = \text{span}\{Ar_0, A^2r_0, \dots, A^m r_0\}.$$

Let $X_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times s}$ be an initial guess and the corresponding residual is $R_0 = C - AX_0B + X_0$. The block GMRES algorithm, at the m th step, constructs the approximation solution X_m to the solution of (1) such that

$$X_m = X_0 + Z_m \quad \text{s.t.} \quad Z_m \in GK_m(A, R_0, B), \quad (5)$$

with F-orthogonality relation

$$R_m = C - AX_mB + X_m \perp_F AGK_m(A, R_0, B)B. \quad (6)$$

In theorem 3, we show that F-orthogonality (6) is equivalent to minimization problem (7).

Theorem 3. Let A and B be two arbitrary matrices. Let X_0 be an initial guess and R_0 is its corresponding residual. Then a matrix X_m is the result of an oblique projection method onto $GK_m(A, R_0, B)$ and F-orthogonal to $AGK_m(A, R_0, B)B$ if and only if it minimizes the F-norm of the residual matrix $R = C - AXB + X$ over $X \in X_0 + GK_m(A, R_0, B)$, i.e, if and only if

$$\|R_m\|_F = \min_{X \in X_0 + GK_m(A, R_0, B)} \|R\|_F, \quad \text{where } R_m = C - AX_mB + X_m.$$

Therefore, the F-orthogonality (6) is equivalent to minimizing the Frobenius norm of the residual

$$\|R_m\|_F = \min_{Z \in GK_m(A, R_0, B)} \|C - A(X_0 + Z)B + X_0 + Z\|_F \quad (7)$$

i.e. X_m solves the minimization problem (7). Consider the F-orthogonal basis V_m , constructed with algorithm 1. Application of m steps of the algorithm 1 to the matrices A and B with the nonzero residual matrix R_0 yields theorem 1. The least squares problem (7) can be reformulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \|C - A(X_0 + Z)B + X_0 + Z\|_F \\ &= \|C - A(X_0 + V_m * y_m)B + X_0 + V_m * y_m\|_F \\ &= \|R_0 - A(V_m * y_m)B + V_m * y_m\|_F \\ &= \|R_0 - (AV_m(I_m \otimes B)) * y_m + V_m * y_m\|_F. \end{aligned}$$

By * product properties and theorem 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \|R_0 - (AV_m(I_m \otimes B) - V_m) * y_m\|_F \\ &= \| \|R_0\|_F V_1 - (V_{m+1} * (\bar{H}_m - \begin{pmatrix} I_m \\ 0_{s \times m} \end{pmatrix})) * y_m \|_F \\ &= \|V_{m+1} * (\|R_0\|_F e_1 - \begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix} y_m) \|_F \\ &= \| \|R_0\|_F e_1 - \begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix} y_m \|_2. \end{aligned}$$

The above results are summarized in the following theorem.

Theorem 4. At step m , the approximation solution X_m produced by the block GMRES method is given by $X_m = X_0 + V_m * y_m$ where y_m is the solution of the following small least square problem

$$y_m = \arg \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^m} \| \|R_0\|_F e_1 - \begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix} y \|_2, \quad (8)$$

where e_1 is the first unit vector of \mathbb{R}^{m+1} .

The minimization (8) can be solved by the QR factorization of $\begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix}$ with Givens rotations.

By algorithm 1, the $\begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix}$ is an unreduced semi upper Hessenberg matrix and $\text{rank}(\begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix}) = m$. Then, there is an orthogonal matrix $Q_m \in \mathbb{R}^{(m+1) \times (m+1)}$ and an invertible upper triangular matrix $R_m^- \in \mathbb{R}^{(m) \times (m)}$ such that

$$\begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix} = Q_m \begin{pmatrix} \bar{R}_m \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

With substitution (9) into (8), we obtain

$$\|R_m\|_F = \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^m} \| \|R_0\|_F (Q_m^T e_1) - \begin{pmatrix} \bar{R}_m \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} y \|_2$$

for obtaining y_m , we solve the following upper triangular system:

$$\bar{R}_m y = \|R_0\|_F (I_m, 0) (Q_m^T e_1).$$

Then, we get the BGMRES iterative solution to (1),

$$X_m = X_0 + V_m * y_m.$$

It can be easily shown that the residual matrix form is as:

Theorem 5. The residual matrix at step m , $R_m = C - AX_mB + X_m$ produced by the block GMRES for the linear matrix equation satisfies the following properties

$$R_m = \gamma_{m+1} V_{m+1} * (Q_m e_{m+1}),$$

and

$$\|R_m\|_F = |\gamma_{m+1}|,$$

where $\gamma_{m+1} = \|R_0\|_F Q_m^T e_1$ and $e_{m+1} = (0, \dots, 0, 1)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{m+1}$.

is the last component of the vector

the vector

Finally, the previous results can summarized in the following algorithm.

Algorithm 2 The block GMRES algorithm (BGMRES)

Require: $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$, an initial guess matrix $X_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times s}$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and ε .

Ensure: The solution X_m .

- 1: $R_0 = C - AX_0B + X_0, \beta = \|R_0\|_F, V_1 = \frac{0}{\beta}$
Compute;
- 2: Construct the F-orthonormal basis V_1, V_2, \dots, V_{m+1} and the semi upper Hessenberg matrix $H_{\cdot, m}^-$ by Algorithm 1;
- 3: Solve the least squares problem
$$y_m = \arg \min_{y \in \mathbb{R}^m} \left\| \|R_0\|_F (Q_m^T e_1) - \begin{pmatrix} \bar{R}_m \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} y \right\|_2$$
- 4: Compute: $X_m = X_0 + V_m * y_m$;
- 5: Compute the residual $R_m = C - AX_mB + X_m$ and $\|R_m\|_F$ by using Theorem 1;
- 6: **if** $\|R_m\|_F < \varepsilon$
then 8: Stop;
- 9: end if
- 10: set $X_0 = X_m$ Go to 1;

In the next section, we construct the polynomial preconditioned BGMRES based on BGMRES.

III. POLYNOMIAL PRECONDITIONING

Consider the generalized Sylvester matrix equation (1). In Section II, we will show that this equation can be solved by the block GMRES method, however this method may slow down the convergence. In order to accelerate the convergence, we construct a polynomial preconditioned BGMRES based on BGMRES. Let $X_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times s}$ be an initial guess and $R_0 = C - AX_0B + X_0$ is its corresponding residual. Define the $n \times ms$ block matrix K_m as:

$$K_m = [R_0, AR_0B, \dots, A^{m-1}R_0B^{m-1}]. \quad (10)$$

Assume that Algorithm 1 does not stop before the m th step. Then by relation 1 from the theorem 1, we get

$$V_{m+1} = h_{m+1, m}^{-1} (AV_mB - V_m * H_{\cdot, m}), \quad (11)$$

where

$$H_{\cdot, m} = (h_{1m}, \dots, h_{mm})^T.$$

Since the space generated by the matrix K_m is the same as the space spanned by the matrix V_m . Therefore, we have

$$V_m = K_m * S_m, \quad (12)$$

where S_m is an upper triangular matrix

$$S_m = \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & \dots & s_{1m} \\ & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & & s_{mm} \end{bmatrix}$$

By Kronecker and * product properties, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V_m * H_{\cdot, m} &= (K_m * S_m) * H_{\cdot, m} \\ &= K_m * (S_m H_{\cdot, m}) \\ &= [K_m, A^m R_0 B^m] * \begin{pmatrix} S_m H_{\cdot, m} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= K_{m+1} * \begin{pmatrix} S_m H_{\cdot, m} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Since $AV_m(I_m \otimes B) = (AK_m(I_m \otimes B)) * S_m$, then

$$\begin{aligned} AV_mB &= (AK_m(I_m \otimes B)) * S_{\cdot, m} \\ &= (AR_0B, A^2R_0B^2, \dots, A^mR_0B^m) * S_{\cdot, m} \\ &= K_{m+1} * \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ S_{\cdot, m} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

By substitution (13) and (14) into (11), we obtain

$$V_{m+1} = K_{m+1} * (h_{m+1, m}^{-1} [\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ S_{\cdot, m} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} S_m H_{\cdot, m} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}]) \quad (15)$$

Since $V_{m+1} = K_{m+1} * S_{m+1}$, then

$$V_{m+1} = K_{m+1} * S_{\cdot, m+1}. \quad (16)$$

From relations (15), (16) and linearly independent columns of the K_{m+1} , we conclude

$$S_{\cdot, m+1} = h_{m+1, m}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ S_{\cdot, m} \end{pmatrix} - h_{m+1, m}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} S_m H_{\cdot, m} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

In the sequel, consider the approximation solution X_m that by using BGMRES method is obtained

$$X_m = X_0 + V_m * y_m.$$

Since $V_m * y_m = K_m * (S_m y_m)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} R_m &= R_0 - AX_mB + X_m \\ &= R_0 - A(V_m * y_m)B + V_m * y_m \\ &= R_0 - (AK_m(I_m \otimes B)) * S_m y_m + K_m * S_m y_m \\ &= R_0 - (AK_m(I_m \otimes B) - K_m) * S_m y_m. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Then by applying $\text{vec}(\cdot)$ operator on equation (18), we get $\text{vec}(R_m) =$ (19)

$$\begin{aligned} &(I_{ns} - (B^T \otimes A - I_{ns}) \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j ((B^T)^j \otimes A^j)) \text{vec}(R_0) \\ &= P(B^T; A) \text{vec}(R_0) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where

$$(a_0, \dots, a_{m-1})^T = S_m y_m, \quad (21)$$

and the residual polynomial is as:

$$P_m(x,y) = 1 - (xy - 1)Q_{m-1}(x,y), \tag{22}$$

where

$$Q_{m-1}(x,y) = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j x^j y^j \tag{23}$$

From (22), we have $P_m^{-1} \approx Q_m Q_{-1m}(B^{-1T}; x, yA)$. Therefore, we can apply $P_m^{-1}(x, y) = 1 - (xyP_m - (x, y1))$ and $(B^T \otimes A - I_{ns})^{-1}$ as the preconditioner polynomial. We must solve the linear equation system:

$$Q_{m-1}(B^T; A)(B^T \otimes A - I_{ns}) \text{vec}(X) = Q_{m-1}(B^T; A) \text{vec}(C) \tag{24}$$

by using BGMRES. The algorithm BGMRES, at the k th step, constructs the approximate solution X_k to the solution (24) such that

$$X_k = X_0 + Z_k \quad \text{s.t.} \quad Z_k \in \mathcal{GK}_k(A, R_0, B) \tag{25}$$

and with F-orthogonality relation

$$R_k = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j A^j C B^j - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j (A^{j+1} X_k B^{j+1} - A^j X_k B^j) \perp_F \mathcal{AGK}_k(A, R_0, B)B.$$

The above F-orthogonal relation is equivalent to the following relation:

$$\|R_k\|_F = \min_{Z \in \mathcal{GK}_k(A, R_0, B)} \|R\|_F, \tag{26}$$

where

$$R = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j (A^j C B^j - (A^{j+1}(X_0 + Z)B^{j+1} - A^j(X_0 + Z)B^j))$$

Consider F-orthonormal basis V_k , which is constructed by using algorithm 1. After k th step of algorithm 1 to the matrices with the nonzero residual matrix R_0 , we can rewrite the relation (26) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j A^j C B^j - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j (A^{j+1}(X_0 + Z)B^{j+1} - A^j(X_0 + Z)B^j) \right\|_F \\ &= \left\| \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j A^j C B^j - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j (A^{j+1}(X_0 + V_k * y_k)B^{j+1} - A^j(X_0 + V_k * y_k)B^j) \right\|_F \\ &= \|R_0 - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j (A^{j+1}(V_k * y_k)B^{j+1} - A^j(V_k * y_k)B^j)\|_F \\ &= \|R_0 - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j (A^{j+1}V_k(I_k \otimes B^{j+1}) - A^jV_k(I_k \otimes B^j)) * y_k\|_F. \end{aligned}$$

By * product properties and theorem 1, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \|R_0 - (-a_0V_k + (a_0 - a_1)AV_k(I_k \otimes B) + (a_1 - a_2)A^2V_k(I_k \otimes B^2) + \dots + (a_{m-2} - a_{m-1})A^{m-1}V_k(I_k \otimes B^{m-1}) + a_{m-1}A^mV_k(I_k \otimes B^m)) * y_k\|_F \\ &= \|R_0 - (-a_0V_k + (a_0 - a_1)V_{k+1}(\bar{H}_k \otimes I_s) + (a_1 - a_2)V_{k+2}(\bar{H}_{k+1}\bar{H}_k \otimes I_s) + \dots + (a_{m-2} - a_{m-1})V_{k+m-1}(\bar{H}_{k+m-2}\dots\bar{H}_k \otimes I_s) + a_{m-1}V_{k+m}(\bar{H}_{k+m-1}\dots\bar{H}_k \otimes I_s)) * y_k\|_F \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &= \|V_{m+k}(\|R_0\|_F(e_1 \otimes I_s) - (-a_0 \begin{pmatrix} I_k \\ 0_{m,k} \end{pmatrix} \otimes I_s) + (a_0 - a_1) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{H}_k \\ 0_{m-1,k} \end{pmatrix} \otimes I_s) + (a_1 - a_2) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{H}_{k+1}\bar{H}_k \\ 0_{m-2,k} \end{pmatrix} \otimes I_s) + \dots + (a_{m-2} - a_{m-1}) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{H}_{k+m-2}\dots\bar{H}_k \\ 0_{1,k} \end{pmatrix} \otimes I_s) + a_{m-1}(\bar{H}_{k+m-1}\dots\bar{H}_k \otimes I_s)) * y_k\|_F \\ &= \| \|R_0\|_F e_1 - (-a_0 \begin{pmatrix} I_k \\ 0_m \end{pmatrix} + \sum_{j=0}^{m-2} (a_j - a_{j+1}) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{H}_{k+j}\dots\bar{H}_k \\ 0_{m-1-j,k} \end{pmatrix}) + a_{m-1}(\bar{H}_{k+m-1}\dots\bar{H}_k) y_k \|_2. \end{aligned}$$

The above results, we can summarize in the following theorem:

Theorem 6. After k th step of the algorithm BGMRES, the approximation solution X_k of (24) is given by $X_k = X_0 + V_k * y_k$, where

$$y_k = \operatorname{argmin}_{y \in \mathbb{R}^k} \| \|R_0\|_F e_1 - (-a_0 \begin{pmatrix} I_k \\ 0_m \end{pmatrix} + \sum_{j=0}^{m-2} (a_j - a_{j+1}) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{H}_{k+j} \dots \bar{H}_k \\ 0_{m-1-j,k} \end{pmatrix} + a_{m-1} \bar{H}_{k+m-1} \dots \bar{H}_k) y_k \|_2, \tag{27}$$

$$\tag{28}$$

with $e_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{k+m}$.

The minimization problem (28) can be solved by the QR factorization the matrix

$$-a_0 \begin{pmatrix} I_k \\ 0_m \end{pmatrix} + \sum_{j=0}^{m-2} (a_j - a_{j+1}) \begin{pmatrix} \bar{H}_{k+j} \dots \bar{H}_k \\ 0_{m-1-j,k} \end{pmatrix} + a_{m-1} \bar{H}_{k+m-1} \dots \bar{H}_k.$$

This matrix is transformed to an upper triangular matrix and then by solving the upper triangular system, we can obtain the vector y_k .

Using the above results, the polynomial preconditioner, i.e. PBGMRES algorithm based on the BGMRES algorithm is summarized in algorithm 3:

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, we present some numerical examples to illustrate the potential of the new algorithm with polynomial preconditioner for the solution of the generalized linear Sylvester equation (1). In the following examples, we mainly evaluate and compare the performance of the new method against block GMRES with ILU and SSOR preconditioner [3], NSCG [19], squared Smith and restarted Krylov squared Smith [10], [16]. We use Matlab 2014a on a PC- Pentium(R), CPU 2.66GHz, 4.00 GB of RAM. We use the zero initial vector $\|R_k\|_F < 1e-9$ and stopping criterion $\|R_k\|_F < 1e-9$ for all the

$$4, 5, C = \begin{pmatrix} \vdots \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} (1, \dots, 1)$$

methods. In examples for all the solvers. In

Tables I and II, we note that Iter, Res.norm and cputime denote iteration number, residual norm and cputime, respectively.

Example 1. *In this example, we have tested the BGMRES, BGMRES with polynomial preconditioning, squared Smith (SM) and restarted Krylov squared Smith (RKSS) methods with $m = 5, k = 10$ on selected numerical example from [10], [16]. The convergence behavior of these methods are shown in Table I.*

From Table I, we can see that the PBGMRES is faster than the other methods.

Example 2. ([16]). We consider the continuous-time Lyapunov equation $TX + XT^T = -EE^T$, where T is the matrix TUB1000³ of order $n=1000$ representing the Jacobian of a tabular vector model, and E is a one-column vector such Algorithm 3 The PBGMRES algorithm

Require: $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$, $X_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times s}$, k , ϵ and degree m of $Q_{m-1}(x,y)$.

Ensure: X_k

1: Compute polynomial preconditioner $Q_{m-1}(x,y)$.

2: for $l = 1, \dots$, until convergence do

3: Compute $R_0 = C - AX_0B + X_0, \beta = \|R_0\|_F$

$$V_1 = \frac{R_0}{\beta}, S_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \beta \end{pmatrix}$$

4: for $j = 1, \dots, m$ do $W =$

5: $AV_j; W = WB;$

6: for $i = 1, \dots, j$ do $h_{ij} = \langle W, V_i \rangle$

7: $> \beta;$

8: $W = W - h_{ij}V_i;$ end for

9: $h_{j+1,j} = \|W\|_F; \text{ if } h_{j+1,j} = 0 \text{ stop;}$

11: $V_{j+1} = \frac{W}{h_{j+1,j}};$

13: set $H_{:,j} = \begin{bmatrix} h_{1j} \\ \vdots \\ h_{jj} \end{bmatrix}, S_j = \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & \dots & s_{1j} \\ & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & s_{jj} \end{bmatrix};$

14: Compute $\begin{bmatrix} s_{1,j+1} \\ \vdots \\ s_{j+1,j+1} \end{bmatrix} = h_{j+1,j}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ S_{:,j} \end{bmatrix} - h_{j+1,j}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} S_j H_{:,j} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix};$

15: end for

16: Solve the least squares problem

$$y_m = \operatorname{arg min}_{y \in \mathbb{R}^m} \| \|R_0\|_F e_1 - \begin{pmatrix} H_m - I_m \\ h_{m+1,m} e_m^T \end{pmatrix} y \|_2.$$

18: Compute: $R_m = C - AX_mB + X_m$ Compute: $X_m = X_0 + V_m * y_m;$
 $\|R_m\|_F < \epsilon, \text{ stop}$

17: ; if

19: Compute polynomial preconditioner $Q_{m-1}(x,y)$:

$$S_m y_m = (a_0, \dots, a_{m-1})^T$$

$$Q_{m-1}(x,y) = \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} a_j x^j y^j,$$

20: Compute the solution of

$$= Q_{m-1}(B^T; A) \operatorname{vec}(C); \quad Q_{m-1}(B^T; A) (B^T \otimes A - I_{ns}) \operatorname{vec}(X)$$

by solving the least square problem (28) and
 $X_k = X_m + V_k * y_k;$

21: Set $X_0 = X_k$
 22: end for

that $E(K) = 1/k, k = 1, 2, \dots, n$. The Lyapunov equation is transformed to an equation $AXA^T - X = -BB^T$ with

$$A = (1 - T)^{-1}(1 + T), \quad B = \sqrt{2}(1 - T)^{-1}(1 + T)E$$

see, e.g. [5]. Now, we compare BGMRES, PBGMRES, and

TABLE I
 CONVERGENCE RESULTS FOR BGMRES, PBGMRES, SM, RKSS, WITH $m = 5, n = 500, \alpha = 0.4$.

	BGMRES	NSCG	PBGMRES	SM	RKKS
Iter	Res.norm	Res.norm	Res.norm	Res.norm	Res.norm
1	1.4142	1.4142	1.4142	0.1280	0.1280
2	1.9626e-05	0.0121	2.2823e-16	0.0275	0.0275
3	1.7228e-05	0.0485	5.2886e-18	0.0208e-01	0.0208e-01
4	6.0121e-09	0.0350	1.2740e-18	0.0239e-03	0.0239e-03
5	4.0623e-11	0.1088	2.6130e-19	0.0722e-07	0.0834e-04
6	4.9543e-12	0.0350	1.7657e-19	0.0168e-14	0.0295e-04

RKSS methods with $m = k = 10$ for solving equation

$$AXA^T - X = -BB^T$$

II. The results are summarized in Table

TABLE II
 CONVERGENCE RESULTS FOR BGMRES, PBGMRES, RKSS WITH $m = k = 10$.

Method	Res.norm	Iter
PBGMRES(10)	0.00763e-09	9
BGMRES(10)	0.0247	450
RKSS	0.0997e-09	443

Example 3. The purpose of this example is to illustrate the numerical behavior of BGMRES and BGMRES with ILU, SSOR and polynomial preconditioning and $m = 5$. The matrix $A \in R^{n \times n}$ is a bidiagonal matrix with entries 2,2,3,4,...,64 on the main diagonal, and super diagonal entries 1. The matrix B is the same as A . Also, the right hand side of the generalized linear Sylvester equation $AXB - X = C$ is such that $X = 1$ is the exact solution. The numerical computations are carried out with $m = 6, k = 10$. The convergence curves plotted in Fig. 1. From Fig. 1, we can see that BGMRES with polynomial preconditioning is faster than the other methods.

Figure 1 The convergence results of BGMRES with SSOR, ILU, polynomial BGMRES and NSCG methods with $m = 5$

Example 4. In this example, we use the matrices $A = \text{tridiag}(1+d, 4, 1-d), B = A$ with $d = 5$ and $n = s = 64$ and k

$= m = 25$. We evaluate the performance of the four block solvers. In Fig. 2, we show that BGMRES with polynomial preconditioning is faster convergence than the other methods.

Figure 2 The convergence result of BGMRES with SSOR, ILU, polynomial preconditioning and BGMRES methods

Example 5. The matrices are the same as in Example 4, but $d=8, m=k=10$. We compare the convergence behavior of BGMRES, PBGMRES, PBGMRES (ILU, SSOR). The results are summarized in Table III.

TABLE III CONVERGENCE RESULTS FOR BGMRES, PBGMRES, PBGMRES (ILU, SSOR)

V. CONCLUSION

We have derived a polynomial preconditioning block GMRES method for the generalized Sylvester matrix

equation. It is observed by examples that PBGMRES is faster than some other block solvers.

APPENDIX A PROOF OF THEOREM 2

Since

$$Ar_0 = (B^T \otimes A)r_0 - r_0.$$

Thus Ar_0 is a combination of $(B^T \otimes A)r_0$ and r_0 and $\text{span}\{r_0, Ar_0\} = \text{span}\{r_0, (B^T \otimes A)r_0\}$.

Next, we consider A^2r_0 ,

$$A^2r_0 = (B^T \otimes A)^2r_0 - 2(B^T \otimes A)r_0 + r_0.$$

Therefore,

$$\text{span}\{r_0, Ar_0, A^2r_0\} = \text{span}\{r_0, (B^T \otimes A)r_0, (B^T \otimes A)^2r_0\}.$$

Continuing this, the two subspaces are the same. This establishes the claim.

APPENDIX B

PROOF OF THEOREM 3

The proof of theorem 3 proceeds as:

o

where $Y = AZB - Z$. By (corollary 1.39, [14]),

if and only if

–

$$AGK_m(A, R_0, B)B.$$

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